

Resuscitating Oghu Festival Performance for Enhanced Participation: An Examination of Sustaining Trends in Contemporary Oghu Umuakah Practice

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Abstract

Various aspects of African life are still in the struggle to recover from the effects of colonialism and its attendant neo-colonial mentality. Our indigenous theatre forms and popular amusements are among the worst hit, *Oghu* festival inclusive here. *Oghu* ensemble is practised among many communities in Njaba, Isu, Mbaitolu, Oguta, Oru East and Oru West Local Government Areas of Imo State in South East Nigeria. This festival performance has dwindled so gravely over the years. But there has been some sort of revival of interest in *Oghu* theatre in recent times especially among the youths. This paper x-rays this revival of interest in *Oghu* festival as practised by the people of the old Umuakah Community in the present day Njaba Local Government Area of Imo State. The data for the paper are gathered through primary research methods that employed participant observation over a number of years and interaction with the organizers of the festival as well as some participants-mainly masqueraders. It is discovered that the trends herein discussed and similar ones hold the key to the survival of many African festivals in future as they are in line with contemporary realities. Hence, the work recommends these trends, or the likes, to other festivals that have become vestige or unpopular with the people as a result of neo-colonialism. Yet, it cautions that care must be taken not to loosen the festival performances and indeed other indigenous African heritages to constant borrowings from other foreign cultures.

Key words: Oghu festival, ensemble, revival of interest, trends, African heritages.

Résumé

Divers aspects de la vie africaine cherchent encore à se remettre des effets du colonialisme et de la mentalité néocoloniale. Nos formes de théâtres indigènes et nos divertissements populaires sont parmi les plus touchés, y compris le festival d'Oghu. La fête d'Oghu est pratiquée par de nombreuses communautés dans les arrondissements de Njaba, d'Isu, de Mbaitolu, d'Oguta, d'Oru Est et d'Oru Ouest de l'État d'Imo au Sud-Est du Nigeria. Cette performance en festival s'est beaucoup diminuée au cours des années. Mais il y a eu récemment une sorte de reprise d'intérêt pour le théâtre Oghu, surtout parmi les jeunes. Cet article présente cette reprise d'intérêt pour le festival d'Oghu tel qu'il est pratiqué par les habitants de la vieille communauté d'Umuakah dans l'arrondissement de Njaba, dans l'État d'Imo. Les données pour cet article sont collectées à travers des méthodes inductives d'observation des participants au cours d'un certain nombre d'années et une interaction avec les organisateurs du festival ainsi que certains participants - principalement des mascarades. On découvre que les tendances analysées ici ainsi que celles qui sont similaires detiennent la clé de la survie de nombreux festivals africains car ils sont en conformité avec les réalités contemporaines. Par conséquent, le travail recommande ces tendances à d'autres festivals qui sont tombés en ruines ou ne sont plus acceptés par le peuple à cause du néo-

colonialisme. Néanmoins, l'article finit par proposer qu'il faut tout faire pour ne pas perdre les performances du festival et même d'autres patrimoines indigènes africains aux emprunts constants des cultures étrangères.

Mots-clés: Festival oghu, ensemble, reprise d'intérêt, tendances, patrimoines africains

Introduction

Among the Igbo of Nigeria, there is a wealth of cultural heritage manifested in ceremonies connected with marriages, births, farming and myriad of other social institutions. These cultural activities contain the germs of rich poetry and prose, excellent music and lively drama...

This view of J.N. Amankulor (1981, p. 113) seems a safe haven to begin this discourse. Even though Amankulor was particular about the Igbo in that work, his view above can be rightly said to apply to many African societies. Festivals are prominent features of life in African societies. Important for the present argument is the role of the festivals as events that foreground relevant social issues. Hence, festival performance is a prime artistic institution of traditional Africa. It is among the institutions that have the framework capable of coordinating virtually all the artistic forms of a community. Traditional festivals last for a considerable time- days or weeks. Most festivals tend to have a story or a myth to perform. Various people have their own peculiar styles to the dramatic realization of the story or myth behind their festival.

Each year, various African communities observe performances and festivals which evoke much of the history of a community. Such festivals are usually ensembles that bring together in them all the artistic forms of the community- costuming, masking, drumming, chanting, dancing and others. A festival is a celebration. It is a commemoration to mark a particular event or a situation. Most traditional festivals in Africa are, in the words of Horn (1981, p. 182), "essentially theatrical, some have elements of the dramatic, and some, at times, contain rudimentary forms of drama". Towing this line of argument further, Olaniyan (2014, p. 326) asserts that festival that has in it "theatrical elements like dramatic personae, arena, costume, spectacle, music and dance etc embedded... can unequivocally (sic) be called a festival theatre". This is true of the *Oghu Umuakah* festival.

Usually, a traditional festival is a communal gathering because it involves everybody in a community. This was before the coming of the colonial masters. With the advent of colonialism and its neo-colonial effects on various aspects of African life, various festivals have been so maligned to the extent that many have become vestiges and many surviving ones overtly transmogrified. *Oghu Umuakah* is not spared here.

The *Oghu* Umuakah Festival Theatre

The Umuakah people of present day Njaba Local Government Area of Imo State Nigeria had a number of festivals before they came in contact with the colonialists. These include *Ekere Mgba*, *Ekeleke*, *Emume*, and *Oghu*. *Emume* is a religious festival associated with the adherents of the traditional African religion. With the drastic reduction in the population of adherents of this religion, this festival is as good as extinct in contemporary time. *Ekere Mgba* and *Ekeleke* are but shadows of their former selves. *Oghu* is the only surviving festival among the Umuakah people.

In the process of evolution through time, *Oghu* has lost most of the religious dimensions it may have emerged with. As such, the *Oghu* Umuakah festival as practiced in the recent past is not a festival of worship. Also, even though it takes place just at the time the planting season could be said to be over, the festival is not a fertility rite. M. J. C. Echeruo sees a fertility rite as

...a ceremony designed primarily to ask the gods for children and good harvests. A fertility festival is usually associated with some actual or symbolic consummation of a union between male and female, earth and sky, benefactor-god and consecrated suppliant. Such ceremonies are accordingly Bacchanalian in character and feature orgies of one kind or the other. There is a period of apparent sexual licence (sic) in the ritual pattern of these ceremonies deliberately meant to anticipate the hoped-for abundance of Nature and the gods (1981, pp. 144-145).

The festival is now a purely socio-economic festival meant to adequately occupy the leisure time of the people from the time after planting to the time of final weeding and harvest. A part of the populace still keeps faith with the festival period for lively entertainment “which they have seen many times before, but without any diminution of interest and readiness to participate” (Enem, 1981, p. 249).

Oghu festival is a yearly performance. Usually the council of *Oghu* heads (*Ndi isi Oghu*) determines when the *Oghu* performance of each year comes up. The staging of *Oghu* is based on the delineation of a number of kindreds into groups called *Onu Ekwe* and there are a number of them in each village. Each *Onu Ekwe* has a number of *Oghu* heads but there is a leader amongst them. The *Oghu* heads in each *Onu Ekwe* usually have their meetings to take crucial obligatory decisions which the leader takes to the village council of *Oghu* heads. There also, decisions, rules and policies are made which the village leader of the *Oghu* heads takes to the

The term *Oghu* is used in a dual sense to stand for the festival theatre itself and the individual *Oghu* dance festivals organized during the *Oghu* festivity period. *Oghu* is said to have come to Umuakah from Okwuorji in Awo-Omama in the present Oru West Local Government Area of Imo State. Hence, *Oghu* Umuakah commences exactly eight (8) days after the commencement of *Oghu* in Okwuorji. This usually takes place in the last Orié Ukwu (Big Orié Market day) in May or the first one in June. It should be noted that eight

days make up the market week arrangement (Izu ahia) of the Igbo. Hence, we have the small and big each of Afor, Nkwo, Eke, and Orie market days.

The *Oghu* festivity is arranged in an order to have the beginning, middle and end convention. The beginning is made up of three major events of *Itu Nkwa*, *Ikpofe Nkwa*, and *Igba Oghu* (the *Oghu* dance performance proper). *Itu nkwa* is the very beginning of *Oghu*. On the fixed date for the commencement of *Oghu*, all women and men in each *Onu Ekwe* are expected to bring food and drinks respectively to the house of the leader of the *Oghu* heads in their *Onu Ekwe*. Defaulters are penalized. In the evening of that day, the men and initiated young boys of the *Onu Ekwe* gather at the leader's house to observe the beating of *Oghu* tunes and their dancing. This is followed by eating and drinking and the *Oghu* orature.

The eight day after, the *Ikpofe Nkwa* takes place. This is not marked with any form of performance. The ten villages of Old Umuakah are grouped unevenly into three for the purpose of *Oghu* performance. The first group, made up of five villages, start the *Oghu* process with *Itu Nkwa*. Hence, eight days later, as they observe *Ikpofe Nkwa*, the next group of villages (made up of two villages) observes their own *Itu Nkwa*. Eight days later while the first group of villages observe the *Oghu* dance performance proper (*Igba Oghu*), the second group observes *Ikpofe Nkwa* while the last group of villages (made up of three villages) observe *Itu Nkwa*. Before the proper *Oghu* dance of any village, all major roads are cleared and swept.

Three major days are important during the *Oghu* dance performance proper. They are the day before the day of the *Igba Oghu*, the day of the *Oghu* dance, and the day after it. The day before the *Oghu* dance is meant for the arrival of guests and the preparation of costume, make-up items, props, masks and masquerades, as well as food items and drinks. This day is usually very colourful. It is usually an *Eke* market day and termed *Eke Ure Oghu*. The next day is the day of the *Oghu* dance. It is marked with cacophonous sounds of the beating of *Oghu* tunes, its dance and cheers from bystanders at the various *Onu Ekwes* simultaneously. The noise of people making merry is also not uncommon. The next day is Afor market day and the day of the *Oghu Afor*. It is usually less noisy as the *Oghu Afor* is usually held in one place in each village. Common sights on this day are a large number of people and masquerades trooping to the venue of the *Oghu Afor*. The beginning stage of the *Oghu* festivity ends with *Oghu Afor*.

The middle stage is marked with the appearance of various masquerades, various *Oghu* dance performances organized by villages, associations, schools, and/or prominent individuals. Many of the masquerade appearances and *Oghu* dances at this stage are to raise fund for the organizers. Some are to attract government attention to the needs of the organizers. The ending stage is also usually noisy and eventful. One of the rules of *Oghu* is that *Oghu* activities (beating, singing, dancing and masquerading) are not carried out on *Nkwo* market days. But during the last stage of *Oghu*, these are done on the last *Nkwo* market day of the *Oghu* festivity. The logic is that the masquerades are angry that *Oghu*

festivity of the year is coming to an end; hence, they break the rule of non-appearance on Nkwo market days. Two days later, an Orié market day, the *Oghu* is declared ended for the year at about 7am. By 8am, the youths gather at designated places for wrestling (*Ekere Mgba*).

The *Oghu* dance performance has the pre-production, production, and post-production stages. The pre-production stage involves all forms of preparation for the performance. These include preparations of costume and make-up, stage and staging facilities, props, musical instruments, food items and drinks as well as hiring of drummers and dancers, and production of trophies and awards were these apply. The production stage is the *Oghu* dance performance proper and the various accompanying masquerading. The post-production involves the striking of the sets, maintenance, storage of sets, props, musical instruments and costume, sharing of monies realized as well as redeeming of trophies. The production stage also follows the beginning middle and end arrangement. Efforts have been made here to explain all these modalities and rules to enhance our understanding of the trends in modern day performance of the *Oghu* Umuakah festival ensemble.

Decline of *Oghu* Festival among the Umuakah People

The factors that led to the decline of *Oghu* festival among the Umuakah people are not in any way different from those that affected other cultural life of man in Africa after colonialism. Such include neo-colonial mentality, economic life, urbanization and Western religions. Ofora (2012, p.14) supports this view stating that “Individualism, evangelization, and capitalism affected and changed rural and traditional life” in most African communities. Of all these, the effects of western religions on *Oghu* festival could be said to be the most devastating. This, though, also has some socio-economic undertones. In many communities of South Eastern Nigeria, Christianity is one force that has dealt a devastating blow on African cultural life. John Yesibo attempted a discussion of this in his work “The Church as a Business Firm: A Critical Reading of Kenneth Nnebue’s *End Time* and Teco Benson’s *Wasted Years*.” That work argues that the church has become “a veritable site for entrepreneurial activities” with most of the religious entrepreneurs living “ostentatious life styles at the detriment of their ministry” (Yesibo, 2009, p. 157). Put differently, “secular human experiences are seen as reflections as well as aftermaths of spiritual warfare” (Oha, 1997: 93). This work agrees with the position of Ofora (2012, p.13) that “Pentecostalism and individualism are catalysts that have alienated contemporary youths of Umuakah, Imo State from participating in “*Oghu*” festival”. This situation, coupled with harsh economic realities that have made it impossible for many to afford the cost of participation, has led to the decline in aspects of the *Oghu* festival as is the case with other festivals.

In recent times, *Oghu* festival of the Umuakah people is witnessing a revival of interest especially among the youths. This paper x-rays this revival of interest in *Oghu* festival. The aim is to evaluate the trends that have engendered this revival of interest so as to recommend same, or the like, to other festival theatres that have become vestige or unpopular with the people as a result of neo-colonialism.

Reviving Trends in Oghu Umuakah Festival

Certain trends have caused a revival of interest among the youths of Umuakah towards the *Oghu* festival ensemble. About a decade ago, only the old and very few youths were active participants in *Oghu* festival theatre. This caused worry among the people as regard the fate of the festival theatre in the near future. At present, the situation has changed for the better. One fact about the Umuakah people, as it applies to other Igbo communities, is that they are great travellers. Apart from the fact that a good number of the youths now have improved economic status to prosecute *Oghu* festivities, their travel experiences have also aided these trends in *Oghu* performance and consequently the revival of interest. These trends are herein discussed under the following headlines not following any particular order of importance. It should be noted that these trends have removed certain doubts and accusations of fetish practices in *Oghu* and hence re-assured even many a Christian faithful.

Dance

Oghu ensemble is one festival theatre that relies so much on music and dance. About five major musical beats/tunes are used for the *Oghu* festivity. No efforts have been made to evolve any new ones and there may not be such moves in the nearest future. Yet, there have been modification on the dancing steps used for these tunes. Many recent dance steps have been incorporated into *Oghu* dancing with minor adjustments. The application of such contemporary dance steps as *Galala*, *Azonto*, *Itigi*, *Awilo*, *Alanta*, *Swoh*, and *Kurukere* has been a source of attraction to the youths. It should be noted that most of these dance steps are borrowed from foreign lands but have become an integral part of the Nigerian dance landscape. Efforts are on-going to evolve variations from these major contemporary dance steps and others. Such dance steps are also gradually gaining grounds in the churches in some form of radical spirituality. Many youths attend *Oghu* dance performances to witness the application of these contemporary dance steps to an age long festival.

Songs / Orature

Part of the *Oghu* festival is the singing of the *Oghu* songs called *Abu Oghu*. In the *Abu Oghu*, the happenings of the year are used to form an oratorio. Brave and patriotic deeds are praised while evil deeds are lampooned. The *Abu Oghu* is didactic and has great sociological functions to the community. Special skills are required to excel in *Abu Oghu* and only a few with such skills are seen in any point in time. Those few are usually celebrities in their communities and much sought after. The skill also runs in families.

In recent times, issues employed in *Abu Oghu* go beyond those in the local environment. National, continental, and global issues now form part of the issues employed. Most of such issues are used to create and re-enact dramatic scenarios. They are usually turned into comic skits. The recent trends in standup comedy in Nigeria are also employed to spice up the *Abu Oghu*.

Acting/Impersonation

In *Oghu* festival, there exist a good measure of impersonation of both the living and the dead. Before now, only the masquerades are known to impersonate. The *Egudo* or *Okorocha*

masquerade impersonates, young men is seen as the spirit of dead young men. Hence, this masquerade is energetic, agile and full of life. It is also costumed to portray the masculine muscle structure of such energetic young men. The *Nwaezeokwa*, *Nwokwa* or *Nwaonyeokeneme* impersonate old men and is seen as the spirit dead of old men. Hence, it is usually weak, fragile and sickly. The mask is carved to portray the disfiguring marks of aging. The *Ugbala* or *Nwaonyeure* masquerade impersonate young ladies and is seen also as the spirit of dead young ladies. This masquerade is typified with extraordinary beauty, neatness and elegance of movement characteristic of typical young ladies.

In recent times, the impersonation in *Oghu* theatre is witnessed among the drummers, dancers, masquerades and carving of masks. Prominent figures in the local environment, national, continental and/or global polity are impersonated. Mannerisms in dressing, speech, movement and gesture, imbecility, disabilities and abnormal statures are the most impersonated in such a way that the average people can easily identify them. The impersonations also demystify the disabilities and ensure general acceptance and integration into the larger society. The benefit of such impersonations in recent times cannot be over emphasized.

Costuming

Here, we are not particular about the costume worn by the passive participants during *Oghu* festival theatre performance. In recent times, efforts are made by these active participants to put on their best attire, usually traditional, during the performances. The drummers and the organizers/managers of such performances are usually exceptional here. The *Oghu* performance arena is usually adorned with various colours of the wears of the participants to complement the colourful decorations of the arena.

The costume of concern here are those of the masquerades. The *Umuokorosha* are the dancers in the *Oghu* performance. This group of dancers performs in stationary *Oghu* performances. They are different from the *Ugbala* or *Nwaonyeure* that are itinerant, stopping only at strategic places or on invitation to perform. Apart from mobility, another major difference between the two is the head gear they use. While the *Umuokorosha* use *Mbunishi* (a type of head gear) built with white feathers, the *Ugbala* or *Nwaonyeure* has a specific type of mask carved to wear the look of charming young ladies. Suiting feminine make-up is also applied on this mask. Also, the *Umuokorosha* can expose their faces while sitting and waiting for their turn to perform but must cover their faces while performing. On the other hand the face of the human behind the *Ugbala* and other masquerades must never be exposed in public for women, children or the uninitiated to see.

Before now, *Umuokorosha* and *Ugbala* were costumed in all white silky materials formed into skirt-like attire and worn with white tops. They also wear white stockings and hand gloves. The *Mbunishi* of the *Umuokorosha* is built with all white feathers and white transparent materials used to cover the face of the wearer. The *Ugbala* mask is also painted all white and other shades of colour used as make up for the lips, eye brow and foundational make-up. Other colours can be used for the accessories. Constant use turns these white materials into other variants discolourations. It was then believed that the turning of the white costume into milky colour and other variants and discolourations of white signify the longer years of participation of the wearer. But critics of the festival theatre employed this

as a point of attack. Even the young people showed some form of disenchantment over this use of all white and other variants and discolourations of white.

The recent trend is the use of any colour and fabric for both Umuokorosha and Ugbala. There is a form of healthy competition among the young in colour and fabric combination for these two masquerades. Wrappers of Indian madras cloth, locally called George of different shades of colours are now in use. The accessories help bring out these colours. Since these are contemporary materials and of different colours, the Christian faithful no longer use this as a point of attack and these are attractive to the youths.

This revolution in costume use also extends to the *Ezeokwa/Nwaokwa* and *Egudo* masquerades. As stated earlier, the *Ezeokwa/Nwaokwa/Nwaonyeokeneme* represents the spirit of the dead old men. The masquerades try to ensure truthful representation through costuming in addition to acting. Old pieces of costume were in use. Some of these are most times filthy. After each year's *Oghu* festivity, these pieces of costume are usually hung near the fire place for preservation. This also applies to the masquerade of the *Egudo* which represents the spirit of the dead young men.

There is an erroneous belief that the old people are characterized by some stench. Hence, apart from the function of preservation, hanging the costume near the fire place brings this stench to them. To also achieve this stench, some break rotten raw eggs on the *Nwokwa/Ezeokwa* masquerade. In recent times, modern trends in fashion are used for these masquerades. Also, the preservation of the costume follows contemporary practices including laundry and dry cleaning. Instead of the stench effects of the old, the masquerades compete with wearing good deodorants. This trend is attractive to the youths.

Staging

The *Oghu* festival adopts arena staging. Before now, palm fronds were used to provide shelter at the performance venues. This gives some gloomy look and appearance to the performance venue. Benches were sourced from among the organizers, their relatives and neighbours. These provided tasking labour to the organizers and the youths. The trend now is to use hired canopies and plastic chairs. This is much easier especially now that those who are in rental business take charge of the deliver, mounting, dismounting, and return of the rented canopies and chairs. This is a welcome development as the task of sourcing, caring for, mounting, striking and return of these are no longer there for the organizers. The venues are also decorated now thereby adding to the aesthetics of the venue as well as provide for some income to those in rental and decoration businesses. Some organizers go as far as adding puppetry for variety sake.

Foods and Drinks

Originally only native food types and drinks were used in *Oghu* festival theatre. Such food items as *Ukwa* (Bread Fruit), *Ugba* (Oil Bean), *Akidi/Nwaigwugwo* (Native Beans), *Ihe Aforo afoo* (sliced cassava), *Una* (three leave yam) and native soup types were preferred. For the drinks, palm wine and local gin were more in use. The use of these native / local

food items and drinks made this festival theatre a purely traditional one. This, though, was not without its own short coming. Guests and even indigenes who grew up outside the town found it difficult to consume these local foods and drink contents. In recent times, national and continental food types and all other varieties of drink are also added during *Oghu* festival. It now becomes easy for people to freely invite their friends from other ethnic nationalities. The native food types and drinks are still there for those who are conversant with them or those who are adventurous with food.

Performance Guidelines

Most of the guidelines for the performance viewed to be harmful or outdated have been re-touched in line with contemporary socio-political realities. The masquerades are now prohibited from the use of any hand props made of metals. These include bells, machetes, bows and arrows; metal rattles (*Oji*) and shields (*Eketé Ogu*). There have been occasions of clash between masquerade groups that have led to the loss of lives or permanent physical injury or even disability. This is because of the use of these metal props as weapons in such clashes. Since the banning of metallic hand props, such physical clashes have reduced drastically. More of verbal clashes are witnessed.

Also, only males are active participants in *Oghu* festival theatre. Only in rare cases are some women known as *Ada Echere* allowed active participation. The women are not even allowed to record *Oghu* or masquerade performances, or tap the *Abu Oghu* performance. This extends even to taking snapshots of *Oghu* arena and masquerades in performance. This has been modified in recent times. Women are now allowed to tap, snap or record *Oghu* and masquerade activities. The mass production and sale of such tapes or records are now allowed provided there is an agreement with the organizers. There have also been new rules on masquerading. The masquerades are now made not to disturb girls in uniforms such as students, nurses, trainee nurses and trainee artisans. Those who are of different religious background are also allowed free movement. This has drastically reduced clashes and confrontations.

There have also been some innovations where opening glee performances are added. These take the form of thanksgiving services, opening prayers, and singing of worship and praise songs. Towards the conclusion, announcements are made regarding events in the community. Where the presence of government or corporate organizations is attracted, the anthem and theme music of such government or corporate organizations respectively are also sang or recorded version played.

Timing and Mobility

Oghu festival takes place from either the last week of May or the first week of June through to sometime in August each year. There are exceptions such as during the burial of an *Oghu* head (*Onye isi Oghu*) where a mock *Oghu* performance is held. The organization of the festival theatre was so rigid that no chances were given for the organization of *Oghu* outside this original timing and geographical location. But in recent times, *Oghu* has been seen as the cultural heritage and pride of the people. So some form of allowance is now given especially during certain important functions such as government activities and that of youth organizations. A consideration of the issues of the mobility of the festival theatre is apt here.

The Igbo ethnic nationality is itinerant in nature. Also, the Igbo are known for the use of unionism to solve communal and individual problems. Hence, the presence of a certain number of Igbo people in any foreign land leads to the formation of such unions. This applies to the Umuakah people with double emphasis. In towns within and outside Umuakah where such unions exist, *Oghu* is usually organized during the *Oghu* festive period. The mobility of *Oghu* festival theatre to such towns is allowed. Umuakah people in these towns see this as a rallying point and as sources of cultural re-union with people at home.

Certain level of freedom now exists as regard the mobility and timing of *Oghu*. Where weather conditions do not permit the people in diaspora to hold their *Oghu* performance during the original timing of *Oghu*, they are now allowed to do that some other convenient time. In 2013 for instance, *Oghu* was held weeks after the *Oghu* period because of the weather challenges witnessed in that country that year. Hence Amazano Progressive Union South Africa held her *Oghu* South Africa on 8 September 2013, while that of Akah Aborigenes Association held on 22nd September 2013. Also, *Oghu* can now be taken to other places outside Umuakah and outside the diaspora union arrangement. Such include Government functions, youth cultural fiestas and competitions. For these to be possible, a certain amount of money is paid by the organizers as fine for defaulting in the rules of timing and mobility. The amount is usually minimal that most of the organizers in most instances opt to pay much more than they are fined.

Sponsorship

Oghu festival now attracts sponsorship from cultural minded people and government. This also includes sponsorship from coporate bodies such as telecommunication network providers. Youths who have special skills in aspects of the festival theatre such as drumming, dancing, singing, acting, costume and make-up, and design now make some decent living from *Oghu*. This has brought about the introduction of various forms of awards and/or trophies. In certain occasions, such talented people are given official invitations for all expense paid trips to participate in *Oghu* performance of the unions in diaspora. This includes trips to foreign countries.

Conclusion

The importance of festivals in the African world cannot be overemphasized. This applies with double emphasis to the Igbo society. Affirming this view, Onwuliri (2011, p. 96) submits thus:

Imagine a world without any form of feast or festive occasions.
Life will be too serious, solemn, empty and even boring...
Throughout ages man has devised ways of expressing ideas, issues
and emotions. Men have devised ways of showing gratitude to god
and ancestors for various reasons and consequently commemorate
such occasions. Such activities come in the form of feasts
involving entertainment, and various forms of artistic

performances. In a festival, one can discern the history and life style of the people.

Oghu Umuakah is a festival theatre of the Umuakah people. This festival has over the years been affected by neo-colonialism and its brain washing effects. This has been a source of concern and worry to the old as the continued existence of the festival theatre has been in doubt. A revival of interest in *Oghu* festival theatre has been witnessed in the recent past signaling rays of hope for the festival.

This paper has been a discussion of this revival of interest in *Oghu* Umuakah. It has been established that some form of flexibility has been allowed in this festival. Hence, there have been modifications in the festival which have challenged the creativity of the youth participants as well as aroused and sustained their interest in the performance. The festival has thus benefitted from a syncretization of materials from other cultural backgrounds in the areas of mobility and timing, sponsorship, costume and make up, staging, dancing, song/orature, foods and drinks, acting/impersonation, and in performance guidelines. The festival has therefore been restructured in line with contemporary socio-political and religious realities of the people yet retaining some aspects of its original sacredness. This could be borrowed and applied on other festivals that are becoming vestiges to attempt reviving them.

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